

CHALLENGES AND ADJUSTMENTS OF MIGRATION OF THE FOREIGN STUDENTS OF DE LA SALLE MEDICAL AND HEALTH SCIENCES INSTITUTE IN RELATION TO THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Challenges and Adjustments of Migration of the Foreign Students of De La Salle Medical and Health Sciences Institute in Relation to their Academic Performance

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine whether a correlation existed between challenges and migration adjustments of the foreign students of De La Salle Medical and Health Sciences Institute (DLSMHSI) and their academic performance. The respondents included were foreign students. The researcher used a descriptive-correlational method employing survey and documentary analysis to correlate the two general types of variables: independent and dependent variables. The principal instrument for data gathering was the validated self-made questionnaire with checklists. Findings revealed that the majority were female, aged 21-25 years old, Filipino-Americans, with a longer stay of four years at DLSMHSI. The primary source of income for these respondents was support from their parents. The respondents encountered several challenges, including financial challenges due to concerns about school expenses, emotional challenges stemming from missing their homes and families, social challenges resulting from hesitancy to speak Filipino and consequent isolation, cultural challenges caused by language barriers, and academic challenges involving difficulty with academic work. To cope with the identified challenges, results showed that the majority of the respondents adjusted by spending their money wisely, consistently communicating with their families using platforms such as FaceTime, Skype, Viber, Facebook, IMO, etc., befriending Filipino classmates and other nationalities, studying the different culture and values of Filipino people, and being motivated to study harder to finish their degree. Findings also revealed no statistically significant relationship between challenges and migration adjustment and the academic performance of foreign students.

Keywords: *challenges, adjustments, academic performance, foreign students, migration*

Introduction

Studying abroad presents a significant challenge for foreign students primarily due to the cultural and environmental differences they encounter. The values and attitudes instilled in these students by their parents and peers undergo sudden transformations upon entering schools in other countries. Tas (2013), asserted that adapting to a new culture and values can be particularly challenging for foreign students, given their diverse experiences and backgrounds. Furthermore, communicating with peers and professors poses a significant adjustment for foreign students due to differences in cultural accents. Many struggle to comprehend their lectures because of their limited language proficiency and disparities in pronunciation, resulting in a lack of participation in classroom activities.

Gatwiri (2015) highlights language barriers as a paramount challenge confronting foreign students today, where language proficiency significantly impacts their learning and individual development. As a result, these difficulties, shaped by their subjective comprehension and existing knowledge, affect students in varying ways as they forge personal interpretations and navigate the acculturation process. Additionally, the educational landscape undergoes adaptation owing to diverse pedagogical approaches. The unease felt in a foreign environment emerges as a significant factor shaping their personal and emotional attributes, particularly in the absence of their loved ones.

Foreign students may encounter diverse obstacles that impede their learning experiences, encounter a range of challenges in their educational pursuits, and adapt to their unfamiliar environment. Parallel to this idea is the statement of Redmond (2017), who said that foreign students' adjusting to living and studying in a new country can be difficult logistically but the social aspect of not having a nearby support system can add to feelings of alienation. In the same vein, Mesidor and Sly (2016), professed that foreign students encountered problems in three primary areas of adjustment such as academic, social interaction, and emotional reaction to their novel environment. Language barriers, unfamiliarity with available resources, lack of an established social support system and/or social network compound the problems and often manifest in depression, loneliness and isolation. Thus, studying abroad poses a formidable challenge and requires significant adjustment especially for foreign students who are new in the country.

Baklashova and Kazakov (2016), said that foreign students are extremely important to the higher education of any country for both academic prestige and financial advantage. The authors claimed that foreign students contribute to the multiplicity and internationalization of academic and public activities. Hence, they help the faculty and students to develop their cultural sensitivity and skills in working with people from different social and cultural backgrounds. internationalization of their classrooms, campuses, and communities and enhance the mutual understanding and appreciation of the differences found around the world.

De La Salle Medical and Health Sciences Institute (DLSMHSI) is recognized as a prominent medical school in Region 4-A, known for its mission to be a leading institution of excellence in health professions education, healthcare, and research. The institution's vision is to become a world-class, God-centered health institution dedicated to enhancing the quality of life and promoting health equity for all individuals (DLSMHSI Undergraduate Faculty Manual, S.Y. 2016-2019, p. vii). The institution was established with the aim of

founding a medical school in Dasmariñas, Cavite, Philippines, aligning with the government's strategy of decentralizing educational institutions beyond the capital, enhancing healthcare, and promoting the establishment of medical schools across different regions of the country. The increasing population of foreign students enrolled at DLSMHSI is a manifestation that it is one of the best medical schools in the Philippines preferred by foreign students to pursue their medical course. Their presence brings diversity to the institution, which helps other nationalities understand and learn about their culture. Hence, they promote global awareness and international collaboration. As the number of foreign students enrolled in the institution continues to proliferate, there are concerns about how students adjust and adapt to their environment, such as food preferences, living conditions, finances, cultures, educational systems, and effectively managing time for studies, especially if their countries of origin are different from the Philippines. Some students feel isolated both inside and outside the institution, which affects their everyday living. Language barriers are also a major concern, particularly for students who are not fluent in English. These concerns were raised by some foreign students enrolled at DLSHMSI during the initial interview conducted by the researcher. These challenges and adjustments could have a powerful emotional impact on students' lives and may affect their academic performance if not properly addressed. The researcher believes that the institution plays a pivotal role in facilitating this adjustment process by providing resources and support to ensure a smoother academic and cultural environment.

With these views, the institution is responsible for providing appropriate services and assistance to foreign students so that they can easily adjust to their environment and face their challenges with conviction. The holistic approach and the most effective student learning practices will help foreign students become more responsible for their own learning, both in school and in life. Furthermore, the adjustment period of these foreign students in the institution could be further improved if their personal and professional needs are looked into and given further assistance to enhance their academic performance. Moreover, the support of the community will enhance their overall well-being, social skills, and academic performance.

Considering the background on the academic challenges and adjustments experienced by foreign students when migrating to other countries, the researcher was motivated to conduct this study. In light of these circumstances, it is therefore necessary to find out the challenges and adjustments of migration and their influence on the academic performance of foreign students, reflecting their thinking, views, and perceptions.

Research Questions

The major focus of the study was to determine whether a correlation existed between challenges and adjustments of migration experienced by foreign students at DLSMHSI and their academic performance. Specifically, this research answered the following problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. gender;
 - 1.2. age;
 - 1.3. nationality;
 - 1.4. course;
 - 1.5. primary source of financial support;
 - 1.6. length of stay in the institution?
2. What are the challenges encountered by the foreign students of DLSMHSI in terms of:
 - 2.1. financial challenges;
 - 2.2. emotional challenges;
 - 2.3. social challenges;
 - 2.4. cultural challenges;
 - 2.5. academic challenges?
3. What adjustment strategies are being utilized by the foreign students to cope with the identified challenges of migration in terms of:
 - 3.1. financial matters;
 - 3.2. distressed emotions;
 - 3.3. relationships;
 - 3.4. way of life;
 - 3.5. studies?
4. What is the academic performance of the foreign students during Academic Year 2019-2020?
5. Are there any significant differences in the challenges of migration faced by foreign students when grouped according to gender, age, nationality, course, primary source of financial support, and length of stay in the institution?
6. Are there significant differences in the adjustment strategies utilized by foreign students to cope with identified migration challenges when grouped according to gender, age, nationality, course, primary source of financial support, and length of stay in the institution.
7. Are there any significant differences in the academic performance of foreign students when they are grouped according to gender, age, nationality, course, primary source of financial support, and length of stay in the institution?

8. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges and adjustments of migration and the academic performance of foreign students?

Methodology

Research Design

To obtain clear answers to the problems presented in this study, the researcher employed the descriptive-correlation method. This involved utilizing surveys and documentary analysis to correlate two general types of variables: the independent and the dependent variables. The independent variables in this study were the challenges and adjustments of migration, while the dependent variable was the academic performance of foreign students at DLSMHSI. Demographic variables such as gender, age, nationality, course, primary source of financial support, and length of stay in the institution were included to determine their association with the major variables of the study.

Furthermore, the researcher utilized a combination of qualitative research and quantitative data analysis. Qualitative research, both guided and open-ended, was employed to gather the opinions and views of the respondents and to validate the collected data for the development of a proposed program on migration adjustment strategies. The quantitative approach was employed in survey techniques, such as tallying collected information and data. Additionally, documentary analysis, utilizing school records, provided information on the overall academic performance of foreign students.

Participants

The research population of this study comprised of 32 foreign students of De La Salle Medical and Health Sciences Institute. The participating colleges included the following: College of Pharmacy, College of Rehabilitation Sciences, College of Medical & Imaging Technology, College of Nursing, and College of Medicine. Only foreign students who had completed one semester and were enrolled for the second semester and beyond were included as participants in this study. Newly enrolled foreign students or those in their first semester at DLSMHSI were not included. Purposive sampling was applied in this study.

In the presentation of the results, the respondents were given their respective codes to protect anonymity and in a way that does not embarrass the participants.

Instruments

The principal instruments for data gathering were the questionnaire and checklists for recording data from documents. The questionnaire regarding challenges in migration was adapted by the researcher from 'The Student Adaptation to College Questionnaire,' while the adjustment strategy questionnaire was self-made. The checklist for international students consisted of three main parts. The first part sought information about the personal details of the respondents, such as gender, nationality, course, primary source of financial support, and length of stay in the institution. The second part focused on the respondents' perceptions of the challenges encountered in migration. The third part covered the adjustment strategies utilized by the respondents to cope with the identified migration challenges. This was submitted for validation to a group of experts in education at DLSMHSI, who provided comments and suggestions to enhance the questionnaire based on the validity of its contents. It underwent a reliability test using the test-retest technique.

The researcher conducted documentary analysis, utilizing school records, specifically the general average of the respondents, to provide information on the overall academic performance of the students. Structured and unstructured interviews were conducted with the respondents to gather their views and opinions on their experiences in the institution. According to Surbhi (2017, p.1), "structured interviews use preset questions prepared in advance by the interviewer to be asked to all participants. On the other extreme, unstructured interviews involve spontaneous questions not determined beforehand". Therefore, a research interview (guided and open-ended) was employed to obtain the respondents' opinions and validate the gathered data.

The respondents' response was consolidated and tallied to analyze the challenges and adjustment of migration.

Data Analysis

To have an explicit understanding of the data, the researcher made use of the following statistical measures:

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This was used to determine the number and percentage of foreign students enrolled at DLSMHSI and the demographic profile of the respondents.

Mean. The mean was used to determine the encountered challenges of migration, adjustment strategies being utilized by the foreign students and their academic performance.

Standard Deviation. In this study, this was used to determine the challenges of migration, the adjustment strategies and the academic performance of the respondents.

T-test for Independent Means. This was used to determine the common challenges of migration and adjustment strategies when grouped

according to gender.

One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This was used in determining the significant differences among the common challenges of migration and the adjustment strategies of foreign students when grouped according to age, nationality, course, primary source of financial support, and length of stay in the institution.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Pearson (r) was used to find the strength of the correlation or association between: (a) challenges of migration and academic performance of the respondents; and (b) adjustment strategies and academic performance of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1: What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

Gender

Figure 1.1. Profile of respondents as to Gender

In terms of the gender of the respondents, results showed that there are 13 or 41% male and 19 or 59% female respondents. Thus, the majority of the respondents are female.

Age

Figure 1.2. Profile of Respondents as to Age

In terms of the age of the respondents, the data revealed that 9 respondents or 28% fall within the bracket of 16-20 years old, 21 respondents or 66% fall within the bracket of 21-25 years old, and 2 respondents or 6% fall within the bracket of 26-30 years old. Thus, the majority of the respondents belonged to the 21-25 age category.

Figure 1.3. Profile of the Respondents as to Nationality

In terms of the nationality of the respondents, 8 respondents or 25% are Filipino- American, 2 respondents or 6% are Solomon Island, 5 respondents or 16% are Americans, 1 respondent or 3% are Nigerian, 3 respondents or 9% are Indians, 2 respondents or 6% are Kenyans, 3 respondents or 9% are Koreans, 4 respondents or 13% are Rwandan, 2 respondents or 6% are Chinese, 1 respondent or 3% are Filipino-Koreans, and 1 respondent or 3% are Filipino-Chinese. The results indicate that the majority of the respondents are Filipino-Americans.

Figure 1.4. Profile of the Respondents as to Course

In terms of the course of the respondents, 5 respondents or 16% are enrolled in Bachelor of Science in BioChemistry, 15 respondents or 47% are enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Nursing, 7 respondents or 22% are enrolled in Doctor of Medicine, 1 respondent or 3% are enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology, 1 respondent or 3% are enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Speech and Pathology, and 3 respondents or 9% are enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Physical Therapy. The results indicate that the majority of the respondents are enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Nursing

Figure 1.5. Profile of Respondents as to Primary Source of Financial Support

In terms of the primary source of financial support for the respondents, 30 respondents or 94% receive support from parents, 1 respondent or 3% receive support from relatives, 1 respondent or 3% relies on their personal income. Thus, the majority of the respondents' financial support comes from their parents.

Figure 1.6. Profile of the Respondents as to Length of Stay in the Institution

In terms of the length of stay in the institution for the respondents, 3 respondents or 9% have been in the institution for 1 year, 7 respondents or 22% have been in the institution for 2 years, 3 respondents or 9% have been in the in 3 years, 14 respondents or 44% have been in the institution for 4 years, 3 respondents or 9% have been in the institution for 5 years, 1 respondent or 3% have been in the institution for 6 years, and 1 respondent or 3% have been in the institution for 7 years. Thus, the majority of respondents have been in the institution for 2 years.

Problem 2: What are the challenges encountered by the foreign students of DLSMHSI in terms of:

The succeeding tables present the answers to this problem. The study revealed that the categories of the challenges of migration are the following: (a) Financial Challenges, (b) Emotional Challenges, (c) Social Challenges, (d) Cultural Challenges, and (e) Academic Challenges.

Table 1. *Summary Distribution of the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators in Category 1 Financial Challenges as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Financial Challenges</i>				
1. Worries too much about school expenses.	2.81	1.355	Agree	1
2. Worries about food expenses.	2.47	1.107	Disagree	3
3. Worries about dorm rental expenses.	2.53	1.218	Disagree	2
4. Has a hard time manage my own finances.	2.25	1.136	Disagree	5
5. Has a hard time looking for a part-time job.	2.41	1.521	Disagree	4
Over-all Mean	2.49	1.050	Disagree	2

Legend: OM = Over-all Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; SD = Standard Deviation; 4.21 - 5.00 - Extremely Agree (EA); 3.41 - 4.20 - Highly Agree (HA); 2.61 - 3.40 - Agree (A); 1.81 - 2.60 - Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 - Extremely Disagree (ED)

Table 1 displays the views and opinions of the respondents on the challenges of migration and their indicators Category 1, Financial Challenges. From the 5 indicators, number 1, worries too much about school expenses, ranks 1 with a mean score of 2.81 and standard deviation of 1.355 which is verbally interpreted as agree. This implies that foreign students are concerned about their educational expenses and needs to handle their finances carefully in order to support their school expenses.

Indicator 4, has a hard time manage my own finances, ranks the last with a mean score of 2.25 and standard deviation of 1.136 which is verbally interpreted as disagree. This results imply that the respondents do not find managing their finances to be as challenging maybe because they were able to manage their allowance properly.

An Over-all Mean of 2.49 and Standard Deviation of 1.050 shows that that all indicators of Category 1 are being disagreed by the respondents as their encountered challenges of migration. This indicates that the respondents do not universally agree that financial challenges are their predominant concern.

Table 2. *Summary Distribution of the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators in Category 2 Emotional Challenges as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Emotional Challenges</i>				
1. Missing home and family.	3.44	1.366	Highly Agree	1
2. Overwhelmed with school requirements.	3.41	1.266	Highly Agree	2
3. Has trouble coping with school-related stress.	2.88	1.129	Agree	4
4. Feels exhausted most of the time.	3.38	1.314	Agree	3
5. Feels anxious and irritated for no apparent reason.	2.72	1.276	Agree	5
Over-all Mean	3.16	0.990	Agree	1

Legend: OM = Over-all Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; SD = Standard Deviation; 4.21 - 5.00 - Extremely Agree (EA); 3.41 - 4.20 - Highly Agree (HA); 2.61 - 3.40 - Agree (A); 1.81 - 2.60 - Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 - Extremely Disagree (ED)

Table 2, Category 2, Emotional Challenges, exhibits the respondents' views on their encountered challenges of migration. It can be seen that under Category 2, there are five indicators of challenges of migration. From the five indicators, number 1, missing home and family, ranks 1 with a mean score of 3.44 and Standard Deviation of 1.366 which is verbally interpreted as highly agree. This results imply that the respondents are experiencing homesickness and are longing for the presence of their family members which is a significant emotional challenge for them during migration.

Item 5, feels anxious and irritated for no apparent reason, ranks the last with a mean score of 2.72 and Standard Deviation of 1.276 which is verbally interpreted as Agree. This findings suggest that this particular emotion experienced by the respondents is considered to be the least urgent emotional challenge for them.

An Over-all mean of 3.16 and Standard Deviation of 0.990 show that all the indicators of Category 2 are agreed by the respondents as their encountered challenges of migration. This suggests that the respondents agree that they are experiencing emotional challenges.

Table 3 describes that among the 5 indicators in Category 3, Social Challenges, item 4, hesitant to speak in Filipino, ranks 1 with a mean score of 3.16 and Standard Deviation of 1.322 which is verbally interpreted as Agree. The preceding findings show that the respondents feel hesitant to practice speaking the Filipino language because of their fear of being laughed at or mocked by other students.

Items 5, felt at a lost and feeling deprived by my classmates, and 6, feels rejected by my classmates, both rank 5.5 each with a mean score of 2.06 and Standard deviation of 1.162 in item 5 and 1.105 in item 6, which is verbally interpreted as Disagree. The findings show that the foreign students tend to have positive relationships with their peers and feel a sense of belongingness. This indicates that the social environment among their peers is generally supportive, which will enhance to the overall well-being and adaptation of the respondents in their new environment.

Table 3. *Summary Distribution of the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators in Category 3 Social Challenges as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Social Challenges</i>				
1. Has difficulty dealing with others.	2.38	1.185	Disagree	2
2. Feels different from others in undesirable way.	2.16	1.019	Disagree	4
3. Feels discriminated.	2.41	1.266	Disagree	3
4. Hesitant to speak in Filipino.	3.16	1.322	Agree	1
5. Felt at a lost and feeling deprived by my classmates.	2.06	1.162	Disagree	5.5
6. Feels rejected by my classmates.	2.06	1.105	Disagree	5.5
Over-all Mean	2.37	0.900	Disagree	5

Legend: OM = Over-all Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; SD = Standard Deviation; 4.21 - 5.00 - Extremely Agree (EA); 3.41 - 4.20 - Highly Agree (HA); 2.61 - 3.40 - Agree (A); 1.81 - 2.60 - Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 - Extremely Disagree (ED)

An Over-all Mean of 2.37 and Standard Deviation of 0.900 implies that all the indicators of Category 3 are being disagreed by the respondents as their encountered challenges of migration. This suggests that the respondents did not consider social challenges to be their primary concern.

Table 4. *Summary Distribution of the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators in Category 4 Cultural Challenges as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Cultural Challenges</i>				
1. Has a hard time adapting to norms in the school environment.	2.53	1.218	Disagree	2
2. Has difficulty interacting with others due to language barriers.	2.75	1.244	Agree	1
3. Has difficulty in adapting to food selection/preferences available in the campus.	2.28	1.198	Disagree	3
4. Feels confused with my ethnic, racial, and cultural identity	2.06	1.162	Disagree	5
5. Has difficulty adjusting to the cultural differences.	2.34	1.153	Disagree	4
Over-all Mean	2.39	0.966	Disagree	4

Legend: OM = Over-all Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; SD = Standard Deviation; 4.21 - 5.00 - Extremely Agree (EA); 3.41 - 4.20 - Highly Agree (HA); 2.61 - 3.40 - Agree (A); 1.81 - 2.60 - Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 - Extremely Disagree (ED)

Table 4 shows that among the 5 indicators of Category 4, Cultural Challenges, item 2, has difficulty interacting with others due to language barriers, ranks first among the indicators with a mean score of 2.75 and Standard Deviation of 1.244 which is verbally interpreted as Agree. This results suggest that the respondents face challenges in social interactions stemming from their limited proficiency in the language. It is imperative for foreign students to develop communication skills, either through visual means or by acquiring basic Filipino phrases, to facilitate better interaction with their peers.

Item 4, feels confused with my ethnic, racial and cultural identity, ranks last with a mean score of 2.06 and Standard Deviation of 1.162 which is verbally interpreted as Disagree. This findings show that the respondents did not consider cultural challenges as their primary concern because they have a strong sense of pride and confidence in their identity, which may positively impact their motivation to succeed in life.

An Over-all mean of 2.39 and Standard deviation of 0.966 indicates that the respondents generally disagree with the indicators of Category 4 as being the cultural challenges they encounter during migration.

Table 5 shows that among the eighth indicators of Category 5, Academic Challenges, item 1, finds academic work difficult, ranks 1 with a mean score of 2.88 and Standard Deviation of 1.070 which is verbally interpreted as Agree. The preceding findings show that the respondents are encountering difficulties with their academic tasks. Therefore, it is essential for the institution to provide support to foreign students in adjusting to their new environment, which can ultimately enhance their academic performance.

Item 6, is not satisfied with professors, ranks the least with a mean score of 1.97 and Standard deviation of 0.861 which is verbally interpreted as Disagree. This finding indicates that the respondents are satisfied with the level of teaching proficiency exhibited by their professors.

An Over-all Mean of 2.40 and Standard Deviation of 0.678 signify that all indicators of Category 5 are disagreed by the respondents as their encountered challenges of migration. These findings show that the respondents did not consider academic challenges as their primary concern.

Table 5. *Summary Distribution of the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators in Category 5 Academic Challenges as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Academic Challenges</i>				
1. Finds academic work difficult.	2.88	1.070	Agree	1
2. Does not function well during examination.	2.41	0.875	Disagree	4
3. Does not use study time efficiently.	2.47	1.047	Disagree	3
4. Has trouble concentrating when studying.	2.72	1.170	Agree	2
5. Does not do well academically considering effort.	2.28	0.851	Disagree	6
6. Is not satisfied with professors.	1.97	0.861	Disagree	8
7. Is not satisfied with academic situation (eg. facilities & equipment)	2.34	1.125	Disagree	5
8. Is not satisfied with course curriculum.	2.13	1.070	Disagree	7
Over-all Mean	2.40	0.678	Disagree	3

Legend: OM = Over-all Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; SD = Standard Deviation; 4.21 - 5.00 - Extremely Agree (EA); 3.41 - 4.20 - Highly Agree (HA); 2.61 - 3.40 - Agree (A); 1.81 - 2.60 - Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 - Extremely Disagree (ED)

Table 6 shows the summary of the challenges of migration encountered by the respondents. Among the five categories, item 1, Emotional Challenges, rank 1 with an Over-all Mean of 3.16 and Standard Deviation of 0.990 which is verbally interpreted as Agree. These findings show that emotional and mental health is a dynamic process that affects the well-being of the foreign students. According to Weurlander et al. (2019), students are often left alone with their experiences and feelings and reluctant to divulge their concerns out of fear and be viewed as weak. Accordingly, they seem to prefer to talk to someone they can trust like their friends and family members. Student's concerns relating to emotionally challenging situations were feeling of uncertainty like the insufficient knowledge and skills and perceived negative culture and values amongst health care professionals and in the healthcare system.

Table 6. *Summary Distribution of the Challenges of Migration of Categories 1 to 5 as Viewed by the Respondents*

Categories 1 To 5 (Challenges Of Migration)	OM	SD	VI	Rank
1. Financial Challenges	2.49	1.050	D	2
2. Emotional Challenges	3.16	0.990	A	1
3. Social Challenges	2.37	0.900	D	5
4. Cultural Challenges	2.39	0.966	D	4
5. Academic Challenges	2.40	0.678	D	3
OWM	2.54	1.17	D	

Legend: OM = Over-all Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; SD = Standard Deviation; 4.21 - 5.00 - Extremely Agree (EA); 3.41 - 4.20 - Highly Agree (HA); 2.61 - 3.40 - Agree (A); 1.81 - 2.60 - Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 - Extremely Disagree (ED)

Item 3, Social Challenges, ranks last with an Over-all Mean of 2.37 and Standard Deviation of 0.900 which is verbally interpreted as Disagree. This implies that the institution were able to help the foreign students familiarize with social norms, Lasallian culture and opportunities to engage themselves in the community activities.

The categories such as Financial Challenges rank 2, Cultural Challenges, rank 4, and Academic Challenges, rank 3 provides invaluable insight into the complexities of the migration experience of the respondents. These findings suggest that the respondents navigate a multifaceted array of obstacles that extend beyond mere physical relocation, encompassing financial, cultural, and educational dimensions.

From the above findings, foreign students should actively engage with fellow students, utilize university resources, and tap into local community support networks to effectively address the challenges they face during migration. Forming connections with other international students, participating in clubs or organizations, and accessing counseling services can offer crucial assistance and foster a sense of belonging within the academic community. Additionally, institutions play a vital role in fostering a welcoming and inclusive atmosphere, thereby ensuring that foreign students feel appreciated, supported, and empowered to excel both academically and socially.

An Over-all Mean of 2.54 and Standard Deviation of 1.17 shows that all indicators of Category 5 generally disagreed by the respondents as their encountered challenges of migration. This indicates a prevalent negative perception among respondents towards financial, emotional, social, cultural, and academic challenges associated with migration.

Problem 3: What adjustment strategies are being utilized by the foreign students to cope with the identified challenges of migration in terms of:

The succeeding tables present the answers to this problem. The study revealed that the categories of the adjustment strategies being utilized by the foreign students to cope with the identified challenges of migration are the following: (a) financial matters, (b) distressed emotions, (c) relationships, (d) way of life, and (e) studies.

Table 7. *Summary Distribution of the Adjustment Strategies and their Indicators to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration in Category 1 Coping with Financial Matters as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Coping with Financial Matters</i>				
1. I save a part of my allowance.	3.56	1.162	Most of the Times	2
2. I spend my money wisely.	3.59	1.241	Most of the Times	1
3. I apply for academic scholarship.	1.75	1.136	Rarely	3.5
4. I do tutoring as a part-time job.	1.75	1.136	Rarely	3.5
Over-all Mean	2.66	0.784	Sometimes	5

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00 - Always (A); 3.41 - 4.20 - Most of the Time (M); 2.61 - 3.40 - Sometimes (S); 1.81 - 2.60 - Rarely (R); 1.00 - 1.80 - Never (N); SD - Standard Deviation; VI - Verbal Interpretation

Table 7 reveals the views and opinions of the respondents in Category 1, Coping with Financial Matters. It is interesting to note that item 2, I spend my money wisely, ranks 1 with a mean score of 3.59 and Standard Deviation of 1.241 which is verbally interpreted as most of the times. These findings imply that the respondents demonstrate responsible management of their allocated allowance, cultivating habits conducive to financial health and well-being.

On the other hand, item 3, I apply for academic scholarship, and 4, I do tutoring as a part-time job, both rank 3.5 each with a mean score of 1.75 and Standard Deviation of 1.136 which is both verbally interpreted as rarely. This findings show that the respondents are not seeking alternative sources of income due to academic commitment and they may rely on substantial support from their parents or guardians.

An Over-all Mean of 2.66 and Standard Deviation of 0.784 shows that all indicators of Category 1 are sometimes utilized by the respondents as adjustment strategies to cope with financial matters.

Table 8. *Summary Distribution of the Adjustment Strategies and their Indicators to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration in Category 2 Coping with Distressed Emotions as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Coping with Distressed Emotions</i>				
1. I consistently talk to my family using face time, skype, viber, facebook, imo, etc.	3.50	1.344	Most of the Time	1
2. I regularly talk to our guidance counselor.	1.94	0.982	Rarely	4
3. I make myself relaxed as I enter the school campus.	3.09	1.201	Sometimes	3
4. I make myself at home at DLSMHSI.	3.13	1.129	Sometimes	2
Over-all Mean	2.91	0.886	Sometimes	4

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00 - Always (A); 3.41 - 4.20 - Most of the Time (M); 2.61 - 3.40 - Sometimes (S); 1.81 - 2.60 - Rarely (R); 1.00 - 1.80 - Never (N); SD - Standard Deviation; VI - Verbal Interpretation

Table 8 displays the views and opinions of the respondents on the adjustment strategies being utilized by the respondents in Category 4, Coping with Distressed Emotions. From the 4 indicators, number 1, I consistently talk to my family using face time, skype, viber, facebook, imo, etc., ranks 1 with a mean score of 3.50 and Standard Deviation of 1.344 which is verbally interpreted as most of the times. These findings show that the respondents maintain an open communication with their family members to enhance their emotional well-being and to foster resilience in coping with life's challenges.

Item 2, I regularly talk to our guidance counselor, ranks the lowest with an mean score of 1.94 and Standard Deviation of 0.982 which is verbally interpreted as rarely. This implies that the respondents seldom visit the guidance office despite the availability of the guidance counselor of the institution. The guidance counselors of the institution are trained to provide emotional support and will guide them to develop effective coping strategies. According to Marrero (2019), school counselors play an important role in ensuring that students have excellent educational experiences who provide social-emotional support and someone who vested in the students' well-being and academic success.

All indicators of Category 2 obtained an Over-all Mean of 2.92 and Standard Deviation of 0.886. This finding reflects that the respondents generally agree that they sometimes utilize all these indicators to cope with their distressed emotions.

Table 9, Category 3, Coping with Relationship Problems, exhibits the respondents' views in adjustment strategies. It can be seen that under Category 3, there are four adjustment strategy indicators. From the four items, number 1, I befriended Filipino classmates and other nationalities, ranks 1 with an mean score of 4.09 and Standard Deviation of 1.058 which is verbally interpreted as most of the times. This suggests that respondents believe that fostering friendships with individuals from diverse nationalities can enrich their personal and academic experiences, facilitating connections within the global community.

Table 9. *Summary Distribution of the Adjustment Strategies and their Indicators to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration in Category 3 Coping with Relationship Problems as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Coping with Relationship Problems</i>				
1. I befriend Filipino classmates and other nationalities.	4.09	1.058	Most of the Time	1
2. I attend school organization/s and community service/s.	3.44	1.343	Most of the Time	3
3. I am active in extracurricular activities.	3.13	1.338	Sometimes	4
4. I see to it that I get along with my peers.	4.03	0.967	Most of the Time	2
Over-all Mean	3.67	0.974	Most of the Time	2

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00 - Always (A); 3.41 - 4.20 - Most of the Time (M); 2.61 - 3.40 - Sometimes (S); 1.81 - 2.60 - Rarely (R); 1.00 - 1.80 - Never (N); SD - Standard Deviation; VI - Verbal Interpretation

Item 3, I attend school organization/s and community service, ranks the last with an mean score of 3.13 and Standard Deviation of 1.338 which is verbally interpreted as sometimes. These findings imply that while attending school and community activities is recognized as important by respondents to enrich their educational experience, their participation in these activities varies. Moreover, active involvement in such activities can contribute to a sense of belonging and familiarity in their new environment, fostering a more comfortable transition into their academic and social domains.

An Over-all Mean of 3.67 and Standard Deviation of 0.974 show that all the indicators of Category 3 are being utilized most of the times by the respondents as adjustment strategies to cope with relationship problems.

Table 10. *Summary Distribution of the Adjustment Strategies and their Indicators to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration in Category 4 Coping with Way of Living as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Coping with Way of Living</i>				
1. I study the different culture and values of Filipino people.	3.75	1.164	Most of the Times	1
2. I study Filipino language.	3.44	1.162	Most of the Times	2
3. I visit places in the Philippines to be culturally adept.	3.41	1.341	Most of the Times	3
4. I actively participate in community immersions.	2.84	1.370	Sometimes	4
Over-all Mean	3.36	1.014	Sometimes	3

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00 - Always (A); 3.41 - 4.20 - Most of the Time (M); 2.61 - 3.40 - Sometimes (S); 1.81 - 2.60 - Rarely (R); 1.00 - 1.80 - Never (N); SD - Standard Deviation; VI - Verbal Interpretation

Table 10 describes that among the 4 indicators in Category 4, Coping with Way of Life, item 1, I study the different culture and values of Filipino people, ranks 1 with a Mean score of 3.37 and Standard Deviation of 1.164 which is verbally interpreted as most of the times. This findings imply that the respondents actively engage in studying Filipino culture to enhance their understanding of the customs, traditions, and practices of the Filipino people.

Item 4, I actively participate in community immersion, appeared to be the last in rank as seen in a mean score of 2.84 and Standard Deviation of 1.370. This is interpreted as sometimes. Although this item is the least among the indicators, it is important that foreign students engage in the community immersion as it promotes community involvement and deepen their understanding of Filipino culture.

An overall mean of 3.36 and a standard deviation of 1.014 reveal that respondents sometimes utilize all indicators of Category 4 as adjustment strategies to cope with their way of life.

Table 11 shows that among the four items of Category 5, Coping with Studies, item 4, I am motivated to study and finish my degree, ranks 1 with a mean score of 4.41 and a standard deviation of 0.946, which is verbally interpreted as always. The preceding findings indicate that respondents are committed to achieving their educational goals and underscore the value of obtaining a degree despite the challenges encountered.

Item 3, I maximize the use of the library, ranks the last with a mean score of 3.03 and standard deviation of 1.257, which is verbally interpreted as sometimes. The preceding findings are supported by Leblond (2019), who asserts that spending time in the library is one of the best ways to enhance one's knowledge. Thus, it underscores the importance of fostering library utilization among respondents to enhance their academic pursuits.

Table 11. *Summary Distribution of the Adjustment Strategies and their Indicators to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration in Category 5 Coping with Studies as Viewed by the Respondents*

Category	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
<i>Coping with Studies</i>				
1. I collaborate with my classmates when it comes to classroom activities and attend to study groups.	4.00	1.244	Most of the Times	3
2. I use on-line platforms for my assignment.	4.25	1.078	Most of the Times	2
3. I maximize the use of the library.	3.03	1.257	Most of the Times	4
4. I am motivated to study and finish my degree.	4.41	0.946	Sometimes	1
Over-all Mean	3.92	0.867	Sometimes	1

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00 - Always (A); 3.41 - 4.20 - Most of the Time (M); 2.61 - 3.40 - Sometimes (S); 1.81 - 2.60 - Rarely (R); 1.00 - 1.80 - Never (N); SD - Standard Deviation; VI - Verbal Interpretation

An over-all mean of 3.92 and a standard deviation of 0.867 signify that all the indicators of Category 6 are being utilized most of the time by the respondents as their adjustment strategy to cope with their studies.

Table 12. *Summary Distribution of the Adjustment Strategies of Migration of Categories 1 to 5 as Viewed by the Respondents*

Categories 1 to 5 (Adjustment Strategies)	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
1. Coping with Financial Matters	2.66	0.784	Sometimes	5
2. Coping with Distressed Emotions	2.91	0.886	Sometimes	4
3. Coping with Relationship Problems	3.67	0.974	Most of the Time	2
4. Coping with Way of Living	3.36	1.014	Sometimes	3
5. Coping with Studies	3.92	0.867	Most of the Time	1
Over-all Mean	3.31	1.18	Sometimes	

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00 - Always (A); 3.41 - 4.20 - Most of the Time (M); 2.61 - 3.40 - Sometimes (S); 1.81 - 2.60 - Rarely (R); 1.00 - 1.80 - Never (N); SD - Standard Deviation; VI - Verbal Interpretation

Table 12 shows the summary of the adjustment strategies employed by respondents address the challenges of migration. Among the five categories, item 5, Coping with Studies, ranks 1 with an over-all weighted mean of 3.92 and a standard deviation of 0.867, which is verbally interpreted as most of the time. These results suggest that respondents excel academically and demonstrate resilience in achieving both academic and personal goals despite encountered challenges.

Item 1, Coping with Financial Matters, ranks lowest with an over-all weighted mean of 2.66 and a standard deviation of 0.784, which is verbally interpreted as sometimes. This implies that the respondents effectively manage their finances due to the support by their parents or guardians.

The categories such as Coping with Distressed Emotions rank 4, Coping Relationship Problems rank 2, and Coping with Way of Living rank 3 imply that respondents employ various coping mechanisms to address diverse aspects of their lives. According to Cambri et al. (2019), the Philippines is elevating quality standards and global relevance, particularly in academic programs and services offered by Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs), positioning itself as a promising academic hub on the global stage. Accordingly, the institutions of higher education in the Philippines must ensure that foreign students receive quality educational experiences, recognize their needs and expectations, and effectively support them in achieving their goals.

With the foregoing findings, it is safe to assume that these adjustment strategies serve as effective ways to navigate life's challenges and provide techniques to manage their emotions and mental well-being during the adjustment period. Thus, the institution could assist foreign students in adapting to their new environment by utilizing categories of adjustment strategies. Moreover, this will also enhance the mental well-being of the foreign students during their transition period. In this way, faculty members and administrators of the institution could sustain or improve students' strengths and address their weaknesses by providing additional assistance and closer supervision.

An over-all average weighted mean of 3.31 and a standard deviation of 1.18 across Categories 1 to 5 suggests that respondents sometimes utilize all adjustment strategies and their respective indicators to cope with their encountered challenges of migration.

Problem 4: What is the academic performance of the foreign students during Academic Year 2019-2020?

Table 13 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the General Weighted Average score of foreign students were from first and second semesters of the school year 2019-2020. These scores were categorized using a scale established by the Registrar of the De La Salle Medical and Health Sciences Institute. The grades were presented by the use of descriptors: Outstanding (90-100), Very Satisfactory (85-89), Satisfactory (80-84), Fairly Satisfactory (75-79), and Did Not Meet Expectations (Below 75).

Table 13. *Summary Frequency Distribution and Percentage of the Academic Performance of Foreign Students by General Weighted Average During School Year 2019-2020*

General Weighted Average (GWA)	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding - 90-100	6	19
Very Satisfactory - 85-89	14	44
Satisfactory -80-84	12	37
Fairly Satisfactory- 75-79	0	0
Did Not Meet Expectations - Below 75	0	0
Total	32	100

Number of Respondents = 32

Highest Grade = 93.67

Lowest Grade = 79.64

Mean = 87.83

Standard Deviation = 3.808

Coefficient of Variation = 4.34%

Verbal Interpretation = Data are clustered at Very Satisfactory level

Out of 32 respondents, there were 6 or 19% with general weighted average of Outstanding, 14 or 44% Very Satisfactory, 12 or 37% Satisfactory and 0 or 0% both fairly satisfactory and did not meet expectations. Findings also revealed that the academic performance of the respondents ranges from 79.64 to 93.67 with an obtained mean of 87.83 and standard deviation of 3.81 verbally interpreted as very satisfactory. Based from the coefficient of variation of 4.34, the academic performance of the respondents is clustered.

Problem 5: Are there any significant differences in the challenges of migration faced by foreign students when grouped according to gender, age, nationality, course, primary source of financial support, and length of stay in the institution?

Table 14. *Comparison of the Respondents' Views on the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators when Grouped in Gender*

Gender	Mean	N	SD
Male	2.63	13	.620
Female	2.48	19	.670
Total	2.54	32	.644

$\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$; Accept Ho: Not Significant; Computed t-value: 0.657; df: 30; p-value: 0.516

A cursory look at the aforementioned table shows that the computed P-value of .516 is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 13 and 19 degrees of freedom. These finding reveal that there is not enough evidence to conclude that the views and opinions of the respondents on the challenges of migration and their indicators when grouped by gender differ significantly. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. This shows that males and females seem to have common views on the same items, possibly due to similarities or common experiences in their challenges of migration.

Table 15. *Comparison of the Respondents' Views on the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators when Grouped in Age*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.775	2	.887	2.321	.116
Within Groups	11.088	29	.382		
Total	12.863	31			

ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant

As shown in Table 15, results revealed that the test of significance on the challenges of migration and their indicators when group in age has a computed P-value of .116 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 2 and 29 degrees of freedom. Thus, the hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. Possibly, it can be attributed to the fact that the respondents share common views on the challenges of migration despite differences in age.

Table 16. *Comparison of the Respondents' Views on the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators when Grouped in Nationality*

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.924	10	.292	.618	.782
Within Groups	9.939	21	.473		
Total	12.863	31			

ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant

A cursory look at Table 16 reveals the test of significance on the challenges of migration and their indicators when group in nationality has a computed P-value of .782 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 10 and 21 degrees of freedom. Thus, the hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. This may simply be attributed to various factors, including racial and ethnic differences, as well as social, environmental, psychological, and biological factors.

Table 17. *Comparison of the Respondents' Views on the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators when Grouped in Course*

	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	2.916	5	.583	1.525	.217
Within Groups	9.946	26	.383		
Total	12.863	31			

ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant

As shown in Table 17, the test of significance on the challenges of migration when grouped according to course has a computed P-value of .217 lower than 0.05 level of significance using 5 and 26 degrees of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. Probably because the challenges of migration are perceived similarly regardless of the academic discipline, indicating a common understanding or experience among the respondents.

Table 18. *Comparison of the Respondents' Views on the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators when Grouped in Primary Source of Financial Support*

	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	.826	2	.413	.995	.382
Within Groups	12.037	29	.415		
Total	12.863	31			

ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant

Table 18 showed that the test of significance on the challenges of migration when grouped according to primary source of income has a computed P-value of .382 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 2 and 29 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Possibly, it can be attributed to the fact that the challenges of migration are perceived similarly regardless of the financial background of the respondents.

Table 19. *Comparison of the Respondents' Views on the Challenges of Migration and their Indicators when Grouped in Length of Stay in the Institution*

	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	1.419	6	.237	.517	.790
Within Groups	11.444	25	.458		
Total	12.863	31			

ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant

The data in Table 19 indicates that the challenges of migration and their indicators when group according to length of stay in the institution has no significant difference to the respondents. It is noted that the computed P-value of .790 is higher than .05 level of significance using 6 and 25 degrees of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. Probably, this is so, because the length of stay in the institution may not substantially influence the perceptions and experiences of the respondents regarding migration challenges. This may also be attributed to other factors such cultural adaptation, support systems, and personal resilience.

Problem 6: Are there significant differences in the adjustment strategies utilized by foreign students to cope with identified migration challenges when grouped according to gender, age, nationality, course, primary source of financial support, and length of stay in the institution.

Table 20. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment on the Adjustment Strategies Being Utilized by the Foreign Students to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration when Grouped in Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
Male	3.28	13	.647
Female	3.32	19	.588
Total	3.31	32	.603

Computed t-value: -0.165; df: 30; p-value: 0.870; Interpretation: Not Significant

Table 20 reveals the results of the test of significance on the adjustment strategies being utilized by the respondents to cope with the encountered challenges of migration when grouped by gender. It can be observed in the table that the computed P-value of .870 is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 13 and 19 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference accepted. Probably, because male and female agreed that gender may not be a determining factor in the selection and utilization of adjustment strategies.

Table 21 indicates the test of significance on the adjustment strategies being utilized by the respondents to cope with the encountered challenges of migration when grouped by age. Findings show that the computed P-value of .485 is higher than the computed P-value of .485 is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 2 and 29 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference

is accepted. Maybe because age may not be a determining factor in the selection and utilization of adjustment strategies among respondents coping with migration challenges.

Table 21. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment on the Adjustment Strategies Being Utilized by the Foreign Students to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration when Grouped in Age*

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.548	2	.274	.741	.485
Within Groups	10.721	29	.370		
Total	11.269	31			
ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant					

Table 22. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment on the Adjustment Strategies Being Utilized by the Foreign Students to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration when Grouped in Nationality*

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.183	10	.218	.504	.868
Within Groups	9.086	21	.433		
Total	11.269	31			
ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant					

Table 22 reveals that the adjustment strategies and their indicators when grouped according to nationality has a computed P-value of .868 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 10 and 21 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Probably because factors other than nationality, such as cultural adaptation, individual coping mechanisms, and external support systems, play a more influential role in shaping the choice of adjustment strategies among migrants.

Table 23. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment on the Adjustment Strategies Being Utilized by the Foreign Students to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration when Grouped in Course*

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.840	5	.368	1.015	.429
Within Groups	9.428	26	.363		
Total	11.269	31			
ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant					

A cursor look at Table 23 shows that the computed P-value of .429 is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 5 and 26 degrees of freedom. This findings reveal that there is not enough evidence that the views and opinions of the three groups of respondents on the adjustment strategies and their indicators when grouped by course differed significantly. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. This indicates that the respondents seem to share common views on the same items, possibly due to similarities in their experiences with coping mechanisms.

Table 24. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment on the Adjustment Strategies Being Utilized by the Foreign Students to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration when Grouped in Primary Source of Financial Support*

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.032	2	.016	.041	.960
Within Groups	11.237	29	.387		
Total	11.269	31			
ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant					

Table 24 shows the test of significance on the adjustment strategies being utilized by the respondents to cope with the encountered challenges of migration when grouped by primary source of financial support. Findings revealed that the computed P-value of .960 is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 2 and 29 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Possibly, it can be attributed to the fact that the primary source of financial support may not significantly influence the selection and utilization of adjustment strategies among respondents coping with migration challenges. This may be accounted to their way of spending their money wisely and how they manage their own finances.

Table 25 shows the results of the test of significance on the adjustment strategies being utilized by the respondents to cope with the encountered challenges of migration when grouped by the length of stay in the institution. The data in the table indicates that the computed P-value of .203 is greater than 0.05 level of significance using 6 and 25 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. Probably because the length of stay in the institution vary depending on the respondents' experiences in the community specifically on how they establish stronger relationships with peers, faculty members, and staff.

Table 25. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment on the Adjustment Strategies Being Utilized by the Foreign Students to Cope with the Identified Challenges of Migration when Grouped in Length of Stay in the Institution*

	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	3.057	6	.510	1.551	.203
Within Groups	8.211	25	.328		
Total	11.269	31			

ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Accept H_0 Not Significant

Problem 7: Are there any significant differences in the academic performance of foreign students when they are grouped according to gender, age, nationality, course, primary source of financial support, and length of stay in the institution?

Table 26. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of Academic Performance when Grouped by Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
Male	3.23	13	.832
Female	3.16	19	.688
Total	3.19	32	.738

Computed *t*-value: 0.270; *df*: 30; *p*-value: 0.789; Interpretation: Not Significant

The data in Table 26 shows the result of the test of significance on the academic performance of the respondents when grouped by gender. It can be noticed that the computed P-value of .789 is greater than 0.05 level of significance using 13 and 19 degrees of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significance is accepted. Maybe because it can be attributed to various factors such as individual study habits, motivation levels, or external influences, which may have a stronger impact on academic performance than gender alone.

Table 27. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of Academic Performance when Grouped by Age*

	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	3.700	2	1.850	4.073	.028
Within Groups	13.175	29	.454		
Total	16.875	31			

ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Reject H_0 Significant

A cursor look at Table 27 reveals the test of significance on the academic performance of the respondents when grouped by age. Notably, the computed P-value of .028 is lower than 0.05 level of significance based on 2 and 29 degrees of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the assessment made by the respondents regarding academic performance when grouped by age. Specifically, ages 16-20 and 21-25 show significance. This implies that age may indeed play a significant role in shaping respondents' perceptions and evaluations of academic performance.

Table 28. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of Academic Performance when Grouped by Nationality*

	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	11.250	10	1.125	4.200	.003
Within Groups	5.625	21	.268		
Total	16.875	31			

ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Reject H_0 Significant

Table 28 shows the results of the test of significance on the academic performance of the respondents when grouped by nationality. It can be observed that the computed P-value of .003 is lower than 0.05 level of significance with 10 and 21 degrees of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. Significance difference are observed between the following pairs: Filipino-American to Nigerian, Filipino-American to Indian, Filipino-American to Rwandan, Solomon Islander to Indian, Indian to Kenyan, and Rwandan to Chinese. This indicates that the responses of the foreign students significantly different from each other, as they may hold distinct opinions regarding their academic performance. The notable disparity in the assessment of respondents' academic performance may stem from variations in educational backgrounds, cultural influences, or personal expectations among students of different nationalities.

Table 29. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of Academic Performance when Grouped by Course*

	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	7.980	5	1.596	4.665	.004
Within Groups	8.895	26	.342		
Total	16.875	31			

ANOVA $\bar{\alpha} = 0.05$ Reject H_0 Significant

Table 29 shows the results of the test of significance on the academic performance of the respondents when grouped according to course. The results indicate that the computed P-value of .004 is lower than 0.05 level of significance using 5 and 26 degrees of freedom. The null hypotheses is therefore rejected. This shows that there is significant difference in the academic performance of the respondents when grouped by course. Probably because the academic performance of students varies significantly depending on the course they are enrolled in, or may be attributed to variations in academic requirements of the subject studied.

Table 30. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of Academic Performance when Grouped by Primary Source of Financial Support*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.075	2	1.038	2.033	.149
Within Groups	14.800	29	.510		
Total	16.875	31			

ANOVA $\alpha = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant

Table 30 shows the test of significance on the academic performance when grouped to primary source of financial support. Findings revealed that the computed P-value of .149 is higher than 0.05 level of significance using 2 and 29 degrees of freedom. Thus, the hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. Probably, this is so, because they may have been fully financially supported by their parents which may not have a significant impact on their academic success.

Table 31. *Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of Academic Performance when Grouped by Length of Stay in the Institution*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	6.518	6	1.086	2.622	.041
Within Groups	10.357	25	.414		
Total	16.875	31			

ANOVA $\alpha = 0.05$ Reject Ho Significant

The data in Table 31 reveals the test of significance on the academic performance of the respondents when grouped by length of stay in the institution. It is noted that the computed P-value of .041 is lower than 0.05 level of significance using 6 and 25 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This shows that there is significant difference in the academic performance of the respondents when grouped by length of stay in the institution. Probably, this is so, because of the varying levels of familiarity with the academic environment, adjustment to coursework expectations, access to support services, or engagement in extracurricular activities among students with different lengths of stay in the institution.

Problem 8: Is there a significant relationship between the challenges and adjustments of migration and the academic performance of foreign students?

Table 32. *Relationship Between Challenges and Adjustment of Migration and Academic Performance of Foreign Students*

		Challenges	Coping
Spearman's rho	Challenges	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.377
		N	32
Coping	Coping	Correlation Coefficient	-.162
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.377
		N	32

ANOVA $\alpha = 0.05$ Accept Ho Not Significant

Table 32 reveals the relationship between challenges and adjustment of migration and academic performance of the respondents. Findings revealed that a negligible positive correlation between challenges and adjustment of migration on the academic performance exists, as indicated by the spearman rho value of .050. However, the computed p-value of 0.377 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. This implies that there is no significant relationship between the challenges and adjustment of migration and the academic performance of the foreign students.

Conclusions

Considering the findings in this study, the following conclusions were drawn.

In terms of the profile of the foreign students, the results indicate a predominance of female respondents compared to their male counterparts, predominantly falling within the age bracket of 21-25 years old. Additionally, there was a higher representation of Filipino-American (Fil-Am) foreign students, with a majority enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) programs. Furthermore, the majority of respondents reported a four-year duration of stay at the institution, relying primarily on financial support from their parents as their main source of income.

The null hypotheses of no significant differences are accepted for five variables related to the challenges and adjustment strategies of migration. Therefore, respondents collectively assess that the variables and indicators identified in the survey represent encountered challenges of migration and were occasionally utilized to employ adjustment strategies in coping with these challenges.

The null hypotheses of no significant difference are accepted in the academic performance except in age, nationality, course, and length of stay in the institution. Over-all, the academic performance of the respondents is perceived as very satisfactory and clustered.

The null hypotheses of no significant relationship between challenges and adjustment strategies of migration are accepted. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between challenges and adjustments of migration and the academic performance of foreign students.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented.

Another study similar to the present study employing foreign students not covered in the present study as respondents could be conducted to validate the results of this study.

Since the majority of respondents rely on financial support from their parents, the institution should explore opportunities to provide additional financial aid or scholarships. This initiative aims to alleviate the financial burden on students and their families, ensuring that access to education is not limited by financial constraints.

The institution should develop comprehensive strategies to address the diverse needs of foreign students and implement effective strategies to enhance the overall well-being and academic success of these students.

The institution should develop a comprehensive program aimed at effectively managing and overcoming the emotional challenges faced by foreign students. This program should provide access to counseling services, mental health resources, and support networks to ensure the well-being and resilience of students in navigating their academic and personal journeys.

The administrators, faculty members and staff of DLSMHSI should continue to monitor and support the foreign students during their transition period in the institution by giving interventions such as orientation programs, academic support services, and mentorship opportunities. These initiatives can further enhance students' adjustment process and academic success.

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